

Essence of children's literature in the formation of professional competence

AUTHOR(S): Shodiyev Fakhridin Teshaeovich

Abstract

This paper analyzes the importance of developing the professional competence of a primary school teacher, being able to mobilize opportunities for goodness in students in a variety of ways, and using them wisely to shape children's personalities.

IJOBAS

Accepted 20 December 2021
Published 23 December 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5801670

Keywords: self-awareness, professional competence, student maturity, children's way of thinking, global idea, independent thinking, universal growth, independent thinking, personal responsibility, personal worldview, self-development principles,

About Author

Author(s):

Shodiyev Fakhriddin Teshavich

PhD in Philology,
Head of the Department of Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute
of Samarkand State University, Uzbekistan.

The growing global demands that surround our home planet require competitiveness from every professional in all fields. While this requires professional competence on the part of all staff, it also requires moral perfection on the part of the teacher. In order for a teacher to have a good reputation among students, it is important to combine both personalities. Because a teacher works with the human heart. Literature classes (1) are mindfulness classes, regardless of the stage of education. Knowledge alone cannot enter the heart.

These changes in the development of national pedagogy require any educator to constantly improve their professional skills. Today, from the state, society and the education system of the time, there are individuals who are spiritually mature, striving for all-round perfection, have the ability to adapt to society in any society, are able to start working, independent learning and self-development. requires nurturing.

These requirements are met by a teacher who is able to think independently, analyze his / her work and its results, and model the educational process. In this sense, today there is a growing demand for a competent teacher who knows his field well, can think freely and creatively, is competitive and able to cultivate personality.

It is worthwhile to get acquainted with the essence of this concept, which was previously specific to those responsible for the fate of the nation and the country, especially primary school teachers. The literature on the subject states that competence means the effective use of theoretical knowledge in any activity, the acquisition of a high level of professionalism and competence, skill and ability (8-5).

Competence is the ability of any person, especially primary school teachers, to have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience necessary to work effectively in the field in which they operate. In a same time, this is a concept that means harmony with personality traits (high culture, broad outlook, high level, independent activity, etc.).

The term "competence" has entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. In the eyes of psychologists, this concept allows any specialist to find appropriate ways to communicate in unusual situations, unexpected situations, to use new methods of interaction with competitors, to use the necessary information to perform complex tasks, to constantly learn. Working on it means consistently improving their knowledge, skills and abilities.

A person's competence is a specific component of a person's state of knowledge, skills, abilities and experience, suitable for solving everyday problems related to daily living, professional activity or social life (2). This concept includes areas such as an individual's competence in independent learning, social and civic activities, social work, domestic life, and cultural and recreational activities:

- competence of independent cognitive activity (cognitive network). It includes the ability of the specialist to acquire knowledge in a variety of ways, including from sources outside of educational institutions;

- socio-civic competence (social network). The performance of civic, electoral, consumer and other duties;
- social-labor competence (labor network). A person should be aware of the labor market information about his profession, be able to analyze the situation in it, be able to accurately assess their professional capabilities, take into account and follow the rules of ethics in relationships;
- household competence (family network). Knowledge of the health of the individual and family members, family lifestyle, duties and responsibilities, and other family issues;
- cultural and recreational competence (cultural network). The proper use of leisure time is the activity of a person for the cultural and spiritual development of his personality.

Today's education system should be organized in such a way that each student has the above-mentioned competencies at school.

Professional competence, which is inherent in any field of expertise, means that a person acquires the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the effective organization of their professional activities and is able to apply them at a high level in practice. Professional competence includes not only the acquisition by a specialist of specific knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities, but also the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in the areas required by him (3,4,5).

Everyone, whether they are an educator, an educator, a teacher, a student, or someone in another field, has opportunities to be awakened and productive. Professional competence, like that of professionals in the field of education, means being able to balance these awakening opportunities inherent in the trainee and turn them into productive opportunities, to be able to use all the opportunities inherent in the person for himself. In other words, professional competence is the realization of a person's hidden, internal, that is, arousing ability to do something, to be put into practice. The professional competence of an elementary school teacher is, to put it simply, the ability of students to mobilize these opportunities in a variety of ways and to use them wisely in the development of children's personalities.

The level of professional competence of primary school teachers is as follows:

- when complex situations arise;
- when performing emergency tasks;
- and the judicious use of conflicting information.

Primary school teachers striving for professional competence:

- consistently enriches their knowledge;
- learns new information;
- deeply understands the requirements of the period;
- seeks new knowledge;
- processes them and uses them effectively in its practice.

In recent years, competent training of students has become one of the main tasks in world educational practice. Because the component itself is:

- combines intellectual and practical aspects of education;
- reflects indicators of the standard of learning outcomes in the learning process;
- demonstrates the extent to which a person's activities and culture generalize to one or a number of closely related areas (6.7).

The stages of formation and development of professional competence of primary school teachers can be divided as follows:

- teacher analysis and understanding of professional development;
- planning of self-development (goals, objectives and solutions);
- be able to express themselves, analyze and edit their activities.

The formation and development of professional competence of primary school teachers is a long and continuous process. That is, the teacher must constantly work on himself in the pedagogical activity, be aware of the latest developments in the field, to develop new qualities from lesson to lesson.

The professional competence of a lower grade teacher implies not only the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills by the specialist, but also the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area. Professional competence also requires an understanding of important social requirements, the ability to search for new information, process it and apply it in one's work.

An elementary school teacher who strives for professional competence: consistently enriches their knowledge; learns new information in the field; deeply understands the requirements of the period; processes new knowledge and applies it effectively in practice; uses conflicting information wisely in complex processes and uncertain situations; can have a plan of action in unexpected situations.

According to creative approach to competence emphasized by N.Muslimov and others (8-7) the competence that teachers of elementary schools should possess can be described as such:

- psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy environment in pedagogical practice, to establish a positive relationship with students, to identify and resolve various conflicts in a timely manner;
- methodical competence - methodologically knowledgeable organization of the process of primary education, the ability to select the appropriate methods and tools for educational or pedagogical activities;
- information competence - the ability to find and select from thousands of streams of information necessary, important and effective for the industry, to use them wisely in the practice of processing;
- creative competence - the ability to take a critical and creative approach to their teaching practice, to demonstrate creative skills in their work;
- Innovative competence - the ability to improve teaching activities in accordance with the situation, to improve the quality of education, to

promote new ideas to increase the effectiveness of this process, to successfully implement them in practice;

- communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with each student in the classroom, to listen to him, to have a positive impact on him, to find the appropriate approach to each character;
- personal competence - to observe one's own dress, culture of culture, to enrich and enhance one's worldview, artistic taste, spiritual qualities;
- technological competence - the gradual mastery of advanced technologies that enrich the knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of education, the use of modern technical means, technologies;
- Extreme competence - to make quick and reasonable decisions, to draw the right conclusions in the event of emergencies, natural disasters, technological process failures, which may occur among students, among themselves and their students. to be able to move on this basis;
- assessment competence - originality, uniqueness in the opinions expressed, a simple, concise, but well-founded response, the ability to make appropriate assessments based on the level of critical attitude, etc.

Characteristic of the professional competence of a primary school teacher is the ability to "correctly assess the knowledge of children, to direct them to continuous independent activity and, at the same time, to determine and assess the degree of independence of students' thinking." plays an important role in determining the path of mental maturity. Commenting on this criterion, it can be said that in primary literary education, the originality of the opinions expressed by students during the analysis of any work of art, fine art, the uniqueness of the views of others, even if it is simple. The ability to correctly evaluate a well-founded response based on the level of criticality of the relationship depends on the level of competence of the teacher.

A teacher who does not have an independent perspective will not be able to pick out details that require students to think independently of the object being studied. As a result, students are limited to retelling the content of a work of art, enumerating the basic tools that can be seen in a work of fine art, and their mental and spiritual development can take place in the same environment.

Of course, there are those who say that it is enough for primary school students to distinguish the superficial aspects of works of both genres. This is also the main requirement of the current State Education Standards and programs. But in every class, there are students who are different from the rest of the world because of their intellectual abilities. The point is, such students are not the average victims. The teacher's ability to organize primary literary education at the highest possible level, to create the necessary conditions for each student to receive it at the level of his / her ability, demonstrates his / her level of competence.

Thus, the professional competence of lower grade teachers in the organization of primary literary education in accordance with its purpose is to improve its level,

outlook, knowledge, skills and abilities, at the same time, for their own spiritual health. After all, this work must be done at the level of art. Because this sacred duty is art of not only teacher's, but also every nation's healing and ascension. That is why, as the great German thinker A. Stifter said, "Art is an indicator of the moral superiority of a people" (9-62).

References:

- Husanboyeva K., Shodiyev F., Hazratkulov M. Methods of teaching literature in primary school.-Samarkand, SamSU, 2019.
- Husanbaeva Q. Analysis is a way of understanding literature. -T.: Editor, 2013.
- Kasimova K. and b. Methods of teaching the native language. -T.: Publisher, 2009.
- Yuldashev K., Yuldasheva M. Fundamentals of artistic analysis.-T.: Kamalak, 2016.
- Husanboyeva Q. Literature as a factor for development of morality and inderendest thinking. -T.: Tamaddun, 2016.
- Yuldashev K. Teacher's book. Methodical handbook.-T.: Teacher, 1997.
- Tokhliyev B. Methods of teaching literature.-T.: ANNO'MK Publishing House, 2010.
- Muslimov N., Usmonboeva M., Sayfurov D., Turaev A. Fundamentals of pedagogical competence and creativity. -T.: Sano-standart, 2015.
- Wisdoms of German thinkers.-T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.

Cite this article:

Author(s), Shodiyev Fakhriddin Teshaeovich, (2021). "Essence of children's literature in the formation of professional competence". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 12- 18, **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5801670>, Issue: 12, Vol.: 3, Article: 3, Month: December, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

